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LEARNERS' ENGAGEMENT ON THE USE OF CLASSPOINT GAMIFICATION BASIS FOR ENRICHMENT PLAN

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This study aims to address the issue of low student engagement in Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) classes at Pinamukan Integrated School by focusing on the integration of ClassPoint Gamification. Anchored on the Department of Education's commitment to improve the quality of education, as outlined in DepEd Order No. 42, s. This DepEd Order emphasizes the development of 21st-century skills through the incorporation of technology and explores how gamified instruction can foster active learning. Using stratified random sampling, 100 Grade 8 students were selected to assess their level of engagement in TLE classes.

Findings revealed a significant improvement in students' academic performance following the implementation of ClassPoint gamification. However, challenges were also identified, particularly the dominance of fast learners, limited device access, and discouragement from competitive leaderboards. To address these issues, the study proposes an enrichment plan that includes gamified TLE lessons, Classpoint alignment sessions, inclusive game design, device support and rotation, and peer coaching with teacher training to enhance student engagement further and promote equitable learning experiences.

Keywords: Learners' Engagement, Classpoint, Gamification

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